

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING INTO ACCOUNT NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS IN A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT. The article is devoted to the study of the topic "National traditions and customs" in the Russian language classes in technical universities using project-based learning, which at the same time contributes to the spiritual and moral education of young people based on Uzbek folk customs, traditions and rituals.

KEY WORDS: project activities, tasks of the education system, youth, society renewal, state youth policy, reforms, national customs, traditions, spiritual values.

ПРОЕКТИРОВАННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ С УЧЁТОМ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ В ТЕХНИЧЕСКОМ ВУЗЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ. Статья посвящена изучению темы «Национальные традиции и обычаи» на занятиях русского языка в технических вузах с применением проектного обучения, что одновременно способствует духовно-нравственному воспитанию молодёжи на основе народных узбекских обычаев, традиций и обрядов.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: проектная деятельность, задачи системы образования, молодёжь, обновление общества, молодёжная политика государства, реформы, национальные обычаи, традиции, духовные ценности

INTRODUCTION

The national model of education of any state reflects the characteristics of national demography, politics, economics, social policy, history and culture.

The Uzbek model of education is based on quality - the quality of teachers, students, programs and, ultimately, the quality of knowledge. It takes into account the needs associated with globalization, and is a tool for ensuring a positive and productive role for Uzbekistan both in Asia and beyond.

The invaluable treasure of the state is the youth of the republic. Today, almost 35% of the population of Uzbekistan are children under the age of 16, over 60% are young people under 30. In this regard, the role and significance of educational reforms becomes clear and obvious.

METHODS

In youth policy, the state has determined the basic principles for further support of youth, developed a strategy for its development, determined economic, legal, organizational support for youth initiatives and its public structures [1, 125-132].

Youth policy was recognized as one of the priority tasks, a springboard and a reserve for the development of statehood. The use of the creative potential of youth in the process of renewal of the whole society is a necessary condition for development. The modernization of the country, the success of ongoing political and economic reforms, the liberalization of all aspects of society, the definition of new development prospects, the future of statehood itself are impossible without relying on young, growing forces, minds, ideas and intellect [4, 36].

The level, quality, priorities and objectives of the education system play a decisive role in the full formation of the younger generation. The political, economic and social development of the country actually depends on the priorities in education. Therefore, in the republic they set a course for the formation of a harmoniously developed personality. This has become the target task of education and pedagogical science.

Uzbekistan is a demographically developing country.[6] The growth of young families is expected here, which means that the need for housing and jobs will grow. It should be noted that the country traditionally reveres parents, customs, traditions, rites, rituals and holds sacred the institution of the family. This, of course, leaves an imprint on the process of labor migration both within the country and abroad. Therefore, the issue of the labor force, its qualifications, the basis of education and acquaintance with the customs and traditions of other countries is on the agenda today.

RESULTS

The effectiveness of the process of reforming society directly depends on the thoughts, aspirations, aspirations and plans of the younger generation. In this regard, the issue of educating a harmoniously developed personality determines whether a young person has a sense of national pride, political consciousness and civic responsibility, the formation of such qualities as patriotism, readiness to serve the motherland, tolerance for other peoples, the value of national priorities, the significance of the family and its traditions.

The brightest, most active period in the life of young people is student life. The student's personality culture is formed at the intersection of moral, aesthetic, artistic and physical education. Regardless of the discipline that the teacher leads, having provided for the possibility of productive use of teaching hours, it is important to seize the initiative from the first days of being in university students. Using various forms and methods of educational and educational work, innovative pedagogical technologies, interactive forms of education (discussions, disputes, scientific and reader conferences, etc.), to load student youth with such work that would be both in their favor and in joy. If a student has an interest in a subject, then there will definitely be a result.

One of the effective forms that allows to arouse interest, activity and craving for knowledge is participation in educational project activities.

Given the fact that the Russian language curriculum in higher educational institutions of the republic is based on national values, the mentality of the people and is inextricably linked with history, culture, spiritual values and national traditions, we propose in this article to get acquainted with the educational project on the discipline "Russian language » on the topic «National traditions and customs».

Educational project "National traditions and customs"

I. Project task	
<i>Introduction.</i>	<p>Human activities are varied. And the main place in it, of course, is given to work - physical and mental, transforming the surrounding world, creating material wealth and spiritual values. But human activity is not only labor. These include social activities, family activities, raising children, studying and much more. However, in the diverse picture of human activity, there are also such actions that, at first glance, do not give a practical result and seem devoid of expediency. But there are many. Here on the street in a stream of hurrying cars, we notice the most beautiful, decorated with a doll, ribbons, rings and balloons. Wedding! Young people are accompanied by friends. The newlyweds exchange rings, congratulatory speeches, a traditional glass of champagne sound. And then a trip around the city, then a wedding party. And there are many such examples. These are celebrations in honor of the beginning of the school year, and solemn farewell to the military service, a rural holiday on the occasion of the end of the harvest, the laying of wreaths on the Day of Remembrance and Honor. It is easy to see: unlike many other things that people do and that have practical meaning, actions of this kind are symbolic, ritual in nature. Science testifies that a certain</p>

	system of rituals is an integral part of the spiritual life of any human society.
The problem that needs to be resolved within the framework of the project:	Why people are so eager to celebrate holidays, observe customs and traditions.
The purpose of the project (what it is created for):	Enrich the knowledge of students, expand their horizons, achieve an understanding that every nation has the right to observe its own customs and traditions, to cultivate tolerance.
Final result:	Fostering tolerance towards the peoples of the world, respect for their customs and traditions. Presentation of the results of the work - a collection of "Traditions and customs of the peoples of the world."
Users:	Teachers and students of the Karshi Engineering-Economics Institute.
Project timeline:	Lead time 7 days.
Number of participants:	Up to 5 people in a group
Project product structure:	Oral presentation. Speeches of the project participants. Booklets, slides, multimedia material, books, paintings, photographs, collage, Internet materials. References.
Tasks of project activity	
1. Collection of information about the holidays, traditions and customs of the Uzbek people, the history of their occurrence.	
2. Classification of holidays, traditions, ceremonies, rituals:	
➤ State	

- Military
- Professional
- Folk
- Family, household
 - Distinctive features and similarities of Eastern traditions, customs and holidays
 - Features of Slavic customs
- International
- Children and youth
- National

3. Distinctive features of a holiday, tradition, rite, ritual (information is provided in a test, graphic image, in the form of photographs).

Types of activities of project team members.

1. Identification of sources of information, its collection.
2. Selection and structuring of information.
3. Preparation of booklets, photos.
4. Making a collage.
5. Preparation of oral information.
6. Preparation of slides.
7. Presentation of work.

II. Project work plan

№	Name of participant	Task	The content of the work	Type of finished product	Deadline

III. Guidelines for the implementation of the design task

Phased implementation of the project task

1. Preparatory stage.

- Clarification of the problem, purpose and results of the project, tasks of project activities;
- Identification of sources of information.

2. Planning.

- Study of the goal achievement algorithm

I stage (5)

1. Collection of information on the objectives of the project (text, photos, booklets, references)

II stage (3)

2. Registration of information in printouts and on electronic media
3. Selection of optimal information

III stage (4)

4. Registration of information in the form of a reference book (working version)

5. Report preparation (paragraphs 1-8)

6. Creation of a visual presentation (electronic shell), slides, poster layout

7. Suggestions for oral presentation

IV stage

8. Making a collection of traditions and customs of the peoples of the world

9. Reporting

10. Oral presentation

3. **Execution.**

- collection and systematization of information;
- final product;
- preparation of a report;

- visual presentation of the project (use the secrets of oral presentation);
- defining the functions of group members in an oral presentation

IV. Evaluation criteria and indicators

- Project product – collection (max. 10 points)
- Analysis: similarities and differences between traditions and customs (5 points)
- Report (max. 8 points)
- Project presentation (5 points)
- Oral presentation and defense of the project (2 points)

Total: max. 30 points

The implementation of this project allowed:	To acquaint students with those holidays, customs and traditions that they did not know about before.
	Expand your horizons on this topic.
	Learn to work both individually and in a team (collaboration).
	To instill the skills of collecting and selecting the necessary information, to analyze, compare, identify distinctive features, as well as the similarity of individual traditions among different peoples.
	Process information, use it in specific cases (for example, when compiling texts, tables).
	Acquire the first skills of working in cooperation.
	Demonstrate and consolidate the skills of organizational, independent and creative work.

DISCUSSION

V. A. Sukhomlinsky wrote: "Education is a multifaceted process of constant spiritual enrichment and renewal of both those who are educated and those who educate." This suggests that today we are faced with great challenges to educate and educate young people in the best traditions of society. [5, 14]

The technology of project-based learning is considered in the system of student-centered education and contributes to the development of such personal qualities as independence, initiative, creativity, allows you to recognize their vital interests and needs.

This becomes possible when living a situation of success, when in fact a young person feels needed, significant, successful, able to overcome difficulties. When he realizes himself, his capabilities, his contribution to the common cause, personal growth and character development take place.

CONCLUSION

The history of any nation is always associated with certain traditions that have been passed down from one generation to another for thousands of years. The study of national traditions familiar to students in their native language, with participation in an educational project in Russian, will help to once again reveal the foundations of spirituality and culture, activate the mental and speech activity of students, help to get acquainted with the traditions and customs of other peoples, and will help instill the skills of a respectful attitude towards customs of other nations, tolerance.

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